

Interaction of Charcoal with Acidified Potassium Dichromate and Alkaline Potassium Ferricyanide

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Interactions of charcoals, coated with different amounts of carbon-oxygen surface complexes, with acidified potassium dichromate and alkaline potassium ferricyanide, have been studied. It has been found that charcoals associated with CO₂-complex are far more efficient as reducing agents than those free of this complex or free of combined oxygen altogether. The oxygen rendered available during each interaction has been accounted for either as gaseous carbon dioxide, a product of combustion, or as CO₂-surface complex, formed by chemisorption of oxygen. The chemisorption of oxygen by charcoal appears to be a preliminary step preceding combustion. The interaction with a stronger oxidising agent causes relatively more combustion and less chemisorption than that with a milder oxidising solution.

It is well known that a variety of inorganic oxidants, in aqueous solution, are readily reduced by carbons. However, there is very little information available either regarding the mechanisms of such reductions or the manner of disposal of the oxygen rendered available. There are two possibilities: the oxygen may cause combustion of carbon or may be chemisorbed giving rise to carbon-oxygen surface complexes. It would be of interest to know the distribution of the oxygen in these two forms in the case of interactions between charcoals and oxidising solutions of different kinds. Such investigations are also likely to yield useful information regarding the comparative efficiencies of charcoals of different compositions for the various reduction processes and in revealing if chemisorption of oxygen is an intermediate step in the process of combustion about which opinions vary at present^{1,2,3}.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Charcoals prepared by the carbonisation of cane sugar and coconut shells⁴ were used before as well as after outgassing at 750° and 1200° in the manner described before. The samples were well ground in an agate pestle and mortar and passed through a 100-mesh sieve. The amounts of combined oxygen were obtained by evacuating well dried (150°) samples (2 g.) at 1200° in a resistance tube furnace, allowing the temperature to rise gradually and analysing the gases (CO₂, CO and H₂O) evolved in the manner described elsewhere⁴.

Treatments: Charcoal (1 g.) was mixed, in 500 ml bottles, with 100 ml of oxidising solution containing either potassium dichromate mixed with sulphuric acid, 25 per cent

1. D. H. Bangham and J. G. Bannett, *Fuel*, 1940, **19**, 95.
2. R. F. Strickland-Constable, *La Combustion due Carbone*, 1949 (Collegues internationaux, Nancy).
3. J. D. Watt and R. E. Franklin, *Industrial Carbon and Graphite Conference* (1957), (London Society of Chemical Industry).
4. B. R. Puri, D. D. Singh and L. R. Sharma, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 756.

in excess of the 1:4 molar ratio as required for the reaction :

or potassium ferricyanide mixed with potassium hydroxide, 25 per cent in excess of the 1 : 1 molar ratio as required for the reaction :

The bottle containing the mixture, in each case, was tightly corked and the contents shaken mechanically for a certain interval of time. The room temperature varied from 22° to 27° during these experiments. The fall in concentration of the solution was determined by titrating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid, in the case of potassium dichromate against standard ferrous sulphate using diphenylamine as the internal indicator, and in the case of potassium ferricyanide, by adding potassium iodide and titrating the liberated iodine against standard sodium thiosulphate. The values, in the latter case, were also checked by estimating the amount of potassium ferrocyanide formed by titrating the solution against standard zinc sulphate, using diphenylamine as the indicator, as well as by determining the redox potential of the system using calomel electrode as the reference electrode. The results obtained by the various methods were in good agreement.

The amount of chromic oxide (Cr_2O_3) formed in the course of interaction with acidified potassium dichromate was determined by igniting the residue obtained on filtration. The value was checked, in a few cases, by estimating chromium in the residue.

The amount of carbon dioxide formed during the interaction was estimated by siphoning out the gas from the reaction bottle and analysing it in an Orsat-Lunge gas analysis apparatus. However, in the case of interaction with alkaline potassium ferricyanide it was necessary first to neutralise potassium hydroxide by the addition of hydrochloric acid to drive out the dissolved gas.

The residual charcoal, after each treatment, was washed, dried at 120° and evacuated at 1200°. The gases (CO_2 , CO and H_2O) evolved were analysed as before to find out if any change in the oxygen content had taken place.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amounts of potassium dichromate reduced on mixing 100 ml of 0.1 *N* $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ with 1 g. of the original (i.e., not outgassed) sugar charcoal, after mechanical shaking for different intervals of time, are plotted in fig. 1(a). It is seen that the interaction is fairly rapid and that about half of the reaction is completed within the first five hours. It is also seen that out of 10 millieq. of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ that was added to 1 g. charcoal, more than 8 millieq. was reduced in 60 hr. under the conditions of the experiment.

The effect of increasing the concentration of the dichromate solution from 0.1 *N* to 0.8 *N*, allowing the reaction to proceed for 60 hr. in each case, is shown in fig. 1 (b). It is seen that, at lower concentrations, the magnitude of the reaction varies directly at the concentration but ultimately tends to attain a constant value,

FIG. 1

A certain amount of chromic oxide was formed in most cases, as shown in Table II. This shows that the reduction of potassium dichromate by charcoal takes place in two stages :

It is interesting to note that even though the amount of sulphuric acid added was 25 per cent in excess of the theoretical amount required for the complete reaction, the reaction, at least at lower concentrations of potassium dichromate proceeds only up to stage (a), as the amount of Cr_2O_3 formed is equivalent to that of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ reduced. However, as the concentration of the dichromate solution increases, the second stage, involving formation of chromic sulphate, also takes place to increasing extents and almost to completion when the concentration of the dichromate solution is about 0.7 *N* or more. The fact that the reduction of acidified potassium dichromate can take place entirely in accordance with equation (a) under certain conditions does not appear to have been reported earlier.

TABLE I

Combined oxygen and its disposal in the case of various samples of charcoal

Sample	Oxygen evolved on high temperature evacuation as (mg./g)			
	CO ₂	CO	H ₂ O	Total
<i>Sugar charcoal</i>				
Original	109.76	80.48	111.12	301.36
750°-Degassed	nil	52.2	57.36	112.56
1200°-Degassed	nil	nil	nil	nil
<i>Coconut charcoal</i>				
Original	66.0	56.40	63.0	185.4
750°-Degassed	nil	43.2	54.2	97.4
1200°-Degassed	nil	nil	nil	nil

The reduction of alkaline potassium ferricyanide on shaking 100 ml. of 0.1 *N* solution with 1 g. charcoal, after different intervals of time, is shown graphically in Fig. 1(c). It is seen that the reaction proceeds fairly rapidly to begin with but ultimately tends to attain equilibrium after about 6 hr. when a little more than 50 per cent of the ferricyanide had been reduced to ferrocyanide.

The effect of concentration of the ferricyanide solution on the magnitude of the reaction is shown in Fig. 1(d). It is seen that this reduction proceeds to a larger extent than that of potassium dichromate for the same concentration. The difference in the two cases, evidently, arises from the fact that whole carbon dioxide, a product of reaction in each case (cf. Table III) accumulates in the closed bottles in the course of reaction with potassium dichromate, it goes into solution in potassium hydroxide present in alkaline potassium ferricyanide. Thus the reaction in the latter case has a greater tendency to be carried to completion.

TABLE II
Reduction of acidified potassium dichromate of different concentrations by the original sugar charcoal

Concentration of $K_2Cr_2O_7$	Amount of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ present in 100 ml. of the solution mixed with 1 g. charcoal (m.c./g)	$K_2Cr_2O_7$ reduced (m.c./g)	Cr_2O_3 obtained (m.c./g)
0.02N	2	2	2.0
0.03	3	3	2.9
0.05	5	4.8	4.3
0.10	10	8.4	4.0
0.20	20	12.0	2.1
0.30	30	17.4	1.25
0.40	40	22.2	1.00
0.50	50	23.0	0.36
0.60	60	25.0	0.34
0.70	70	25.8	0.20
0.80	80	26.50	0.00
0.90	90	28.50	0.00
1.00	100	29.70	0.00

The relative efficiencies of the original and the outgassed samples of sugar and coconut charcoals for the reduction processes are shown in Table III. It is seen that the original charcoals, under similar conditions, are far more efficient than the outgassed charcoals. Thus charcoal associated with combined oxygen, particularly that part of it which is disposed off as carbon dioxide (cf. Table I), is far more efficient as a reductant than that which is devoid of this complex (cf. 750°-outgassed charcoals) or is free of combined oxygen altogether (cf. 1200°-outgassed charcoals). Therefore, whenever required for reduction purposes, charcoal containing CO_2 -complex should be preferred.

The amount of oxygen rendered available in each interaction is also shown in an appropriate column in Table III. It is interesting to note that almost the entire amount of oxygen can be accounted for either as that used in causing combustion of carbon to carbon dioxide or as that chemisorbed by charcoal itself, during the interaction, giving rise to CO_2 -complex.

TABLE III

Reduction of acidified potassium dichromate and alkaline potassium ferricyanide by the various samples of charcoal and account of oxygen rendered available

Nature of charcoal	Concentration of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ or $K_3Fe(CN)_6$	Amount of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ or $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ present in 100 ml. of the solution mixed with 1g. charcoal (m.e./g)	Amount reduced (m.e./g.)	Oxygen rendered available (calculated) (m.e./g.)	Account of oxygen O_2 evolved as gaseous CO_2 (m.e./g.)	O_2 chemisorbed by charcoal and evolved as CO_2 on evacuation (m.e./g.)
<i>Sugar charcoal</i>						
Original	0.8N ($K_2Cr_2O_7$)	80	26.5	26.5	25.0	2.1
	0.8N [$K_3Fe(CN)_6$]	80	52.4	52.4	37.8	14.0
750°-degassed	0.8N ($K_2Cr_2O_7$)	80	6.8	6.8	2.6	3.6
	0.8N [$K_3Fe(CN)_6$]	80	13.2	13.2	1.8	12.8
1200°-degassed	0.8N ($K_2Cr_2O_7$)	80	5.1	5.1	2.6	2.5
	0.8N [$K_3Fe(CN)_6$]	80	9.8	9.8	nil	10.4
<i>Coconut charcoal</i>						
Original	0.8N [$K_3Fe(CN)_6$]	80	40.1	40.1	26.8	12.5
750°-degassed	0.8N [$K_3Fe(CN)_6$]	80	7.7	7.7	nil	7.5
1200°-degassed	0.8N [$K_3Fe(CN)_6$]	80	4.1	4.1	nil	3.6

There was a considerable amount of combustion in the case of the original charcoals which were associated with a large amount of oxygen and, as appears from the data (Table II), this is probably the major cause of their greater efficiencies as reducing agents. The outgassed charcoals, by comparison, show very little burning, although they chemisorb an appreciable fraction of the oxygen rendered available. It appears that whereas the presence of combined oxygen promotes combustion, its absence promotes chemisorption. It looks highly probable that chemisorption of oxygen is a preliminary step preceding combustion.

The results also indicate that potassium dichromate, a stronger oxidising agent, causes relatively more combustion and less chemisorption than potassium ferricyanide, a milder oxidising agent.